

ICCM17
Scala Lecture

**FROM ATOMS TO AEROPLANES:
TOWARDS MULTI-SCALE MODELLING AND
DESIGN OF COMPOSITES**

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to describe how the matrix and interfacial chemistry impinge on the micromechanics and macromechanics of a fibre composite. This approach provides the knowledge for optimising performance and reliability.

Multiscale Modelling of Composite Performance

The lecture will begin with recent work on the hierarchical modelling of a composite material illustrating the application of group interaction modelling (GIM) to the prediction of the thermomechanical properties of a polymer. By introducing the predicted non-linear stress strain curve into a finite element model for the calculation of stress concentrations near fibre-breaks, a statistical model for the strength of a unidirectional fibre composite can be parameterised. One aspect of this model involves introducing the elastoplasticity of the matrix into the finite element model. Figures 1-3 illustrate the principle outcomes of these models. The non-linear properties of the resin can be predicted from the fundamental molecular model by including molecular conformational change below the glass transition [1, 2]. The non-linear stress-strain curve for the matrix is responsible for the magnitude of ineffective length at a broken fibre. Clearly a debond will extend the ineffective length.

In the current work we have assumed that the interface is perfect, however by using an ineffective length which includes the interfacial response, the model can be extended. The ineffective length of a fibre at a fibre-break in a composite strongly influences the ultimate strength of a unidirectional composite.

Figure 1: Experimental (solid) and GIM predicted (dashed) compressive stress-strain curve for TGDDM/DDS at room temperature and strain rate of 0.00167 Hz.

Figure 2: Group interaction modelling predicted room temperature compressive stress-strain curves for TGDDM/DDS as function of strain rate.

Figure 3: Predicted failure strain of UD fibre composite as function of length and strain rate

Introducing Interface and Interphases

The ineffective length of a broken fibre combines contributions from the matrix and the stress transfer capability through the interface therefore this parameter can be used to introduce the interfacial response into the model. The data from the single embedded fragmentation test can be used to measure the ineffective length as a function of the interphase and/or interfacial integrity depending on the system [3]. In future, the GIM model will be used to model the formation of an interphase, providing the thermomechanical properties at the nanometric scale. In this way, protocols for sizing of fibres can be achieved. To do this we need to understand the chemical structure of the interphase.

The Interphase in Fibre Composite Materials

The paper will also review interphase formation in composite materials using analytical chemistry methods, Time of Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (ToFSIMS) can be used to identify interpenetrating network formation while X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) can be used to study the interactions at fibre surfaces [4, 5]. Furthermore, the fundamentals of interfacial response in a composite material can be quantified using the photoelastic method. Four-phase phase stepping photoelasticity has been used to clarify and identify the effect of transverse cracks, interfacial debonding and mixed mode failure at fibre interfaces on stress transfer efficiency [4]. In order to marry these length scales into a multiscale model a full understanding of the performance of the composite from chemistry through to engineering is required.

Healable Composites

The understanding described above enabled us to identify techniques for healing epoxy resins used as matrices for composites (Figure 4). At the larger length scale, we will demonstrate how epoxy resins can be made to be self-healable and how, using the self-sensing ability of the carbon fibres, we can identify impact damage and provide a means of monitoring the healing of this damage [7, 8, 9]. It has to be recognised that the healing will occur in resin cracks and cracks within the “interfacial” regions of the composite which involves molecular chemistry. The paper will demonstrate how controlling these aspects can provide a composite with a switchable healing capability (Figure 5).

Figure 4: The healing of a commercial thermoplastic toughened epoxy resin at 180C

Concluding Remarks

The paper has demonstrated how understanding of the changes in the molecular structure of a resin matrix during cure combined with a full understanding of the interface and interphase structure and micromechanical response a multiscale model linking across all length scales can be achieved Gas phase fibre sizing is a practical methodology for realising these goals of material and structural optimisation [10].

Finally, the paper will attempt to show how, in future, all of these elements within a composite material can be brought together in a full predictive model of the hierarchical performance of a composite material. Furthermore, ultimately, to provide the means for designing a composite with the required fracture behaviour and to optimise reliability, durability and fatigue resistance.

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Figure 5: Demonstration of Self-sensing and thermally activated healing of a composite. (a) Triangulated resistance (Ω) of non-impacted NCF laminate. (b) Negative change in triangulated resistance (Ω) after 2.7J and 4.1 J impacts showing matrix cracks and small Scale delamination. (c) Positive change in resistance (Ω) after thermal healing at 180°C for 2 h.

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